

A Service Provider's Guide to Data Sharing Policies

These reference cards convey data sharing policy recommendations to be adopted by data and service providers within the EOSC-hub consortium. Our recommendations contribute to the developing field of data sharing policies in the EOSC at large.

The Why | The What | The How

How can you implement data sharing policies practically? Some examples.

For more details, consult the D2.8 and D2.9 deliverables via: <https://bit.ly/2zDAAnM>

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are long-lasting references to a data object. By using PIDs, you ensure findability and accessibility. EOSC-hub should initiate a programme of technical research for direct retrieval of data objects by PID.

Additionally, EOSC-hub should track the work of the FREYA project and adopt best practices in PID resolution as they emerge. One of the outputs of the FREYA project, is the PID-graph.

Source: PID Chart, Fenner & Aryani, FREYA

Figure: FREYA-project PID-graph of three use cases with digital objects connected by PIDs: different versions of software code (left), datasets hosted by a particular repository (middle) and all digital objects connected to a research object (right).

DATATAGS RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

The Datatags recommendation system gives the user more information about which precautions he/she should take to comply with the legislation about publishing privacy-sensitive data to a data repository.

As a generic service, it can be used with different decision trees and repositories, depending on their IT-architecture. For example, the EOSC-hub-implementation of this tree as a service is being tested in the DataVerse by DANS. The resulting data object tag should correspond to the sensitivity level, based on at least 4 risk-levels: blue, green, orange, and red. Green or higher (de-identified personal data and above) shouldn't be copied or distributed within the EOSC-hub ecosystem. EOSC-hub should promote such tools for tagging data objects and adopt Datatags for data objects.